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GNOSIS 10 (2025) 77–107

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Gnostic and Catholic Appropriations of Platonism

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Received 9 April 2023 | Accepted 1 February 2024 |
Published online 19 February 2025

Abstract

The ancient Gnostic synthesis of Platonism with the Jewish scriptures is evaluated in contrast to that of emerging Catholic orthodoxy. Plotinus' critique of Sethian Gnosticism provides the philosophical context for this analysis. A hurdle for both syntheses was the dissimilitude between the Biblical Yahweh and the Platonic first principle. Catholicism eventually resolved this tension by “telescoping” the Plotinian hypostases together into the Trinity, whereas Gnosticism solved it by denying that Yahweh was the true first principle. The Gnostic synthesis represents a more coherent adaptation of Platonism that leaves open the possibility of Plotinus' vision of union with the One.

Keywords

Plotinus – Neoplatonism – Gnosticism – orthodoxy – Catholic – Platonism

1 The Clash between Paganism and Gnosticism in Plotinus

In *Ennead* 11.9 Plotinus launched an attack against the “arbitrary, arrogant assertions” and “insolence” of those who “just meant to be blasphemous!” by making the Demiurge (δημιουργός) “... revolt from his mother and drag the universe which proceeds from him down to the ultimate limit of images.”¹ Given that Porphyry lists *Zostrianos* (NHC VIII,1) and *Allogenes the Stranger*

¹ Plot., *Enn.* 11.9.10 (Armstrong 1966, 265, 267).

(NHC XI,3) among the works which these “deceivers” circulated, and that Plotinus seems to be critiquing teachings found in *Zostrianos* and probably even cites from it, it seems likely that some form of Platonising Sethianism was his primary target.² Turner notes that these works “... clearly share a metaphysics and ontological doctrine characteristic of Plotinus and later Neoplatonists as well as of certain Middle Platonic sources”³

The ferocity of Plotinus’ denunciations, therefore, might seem to reflect the “narcissism of small differences”. After all, Plotinus holds a great deal of common ground with these heretical deceivers in terms of their overall metaphysical vision.⁴ Kalligas notes “obvious similarities” between Gnostic theology and Plotinian metaphysics, and, as Mazur has demonstrated, it is possible that the relationship between them was very close indeed.⁵

Virulent animosity towards Gnostic thought is standard fare due to its bitter rivalry with Catholicism at a crucial formative stage in the development of the latter. The image of the Gnostic as the diabolical prototype of every irrational heretical absurdity has its origin with the heresiologists of the emerging Catholic church, in particular Tertullian and Irenaeus.⁶ Sympathy towards Gnostic thought is often lacking even in contemporary scholarly treatments of their beliefs, such as when, in an otherwise excellent outline of the origin of evil in Sethian and Valentinian Gnostic thought, Pleše castigates their beliefs as being the product of “anthropomorphic fallacies” and “a conscious misprision of Plato and the Platonic tradition.”⁷

This negative assessment of Gnostic thought reflects long-ingrained prejudices which occasionally flare back into the open. Thus, in the twentieth century, Voegelin and Molnar portrayed Gnosticism as the archetypal “perennial heresy,” and the Gnostics as the thoroughly wicked prototypes of every destructive utopian social and political movement, from Nazism to Marxism.⁸ In the process of developing such polemics, the concept of “Gnosticism” itself has obviously become stretched far beyond a narrow application to the Valentinian, Sethian, and related movements of the early Christian era. The meaning of the term “Gnostic” has become a hotly contested issue within contem-

2 Burns 2013, 169; Turner 2007b, 788; Turner 2007a, 682.

3 Turner 2007a, 682.

4 Turner 2016, 60.

5 Kalligas 2000, 119; Mazur 2021, 1–25.

6 Versluis 2003, 712.

7 Pleše 2014, 102, 107.

8 Molnar 1972, 30–33; Voegelin 1997, 55.

porary scholarship on the subject itself, an issue which it will be necessary to address later.⁹

The hostility of Plotinus towards the Sethian Gnostics, however, had nothing to do with the concerns of emerging Catholic orthodoxy. Plotinus was a pagan, who revered the Hellenic deities and saw the Platonic tradition as encapsulating the metaphysical framework within which polytheism was best expressed.¹⁰ Plotinus' attack on Gnosticism was motivated by what he saw as its inconsistency with Platonic ideas which reflected a widespread pagan confidence in, and reverence for, the goodness of nature and the natural world. This was the "enchanted" world of the pagan deities, a world which was animated by the World-Soul.¹¹ Plotinus' concern is entirely with what he regarded as the perversion of Platonism involved in Gnosticism, resulting in a negative stance towards the natural world. He had no interest whatsoever in engagement with the Hebrew scriptures.

The Gnostics, it seems, managed to arouse the antipathy of both orthodox Christians and polytheistic pagans. If it is true that, as the Sermon on the Mount maintains, "Blessed are you when others revile you," then the Gnostics were blessed indeed.¹²

This lack of interest in the Hebrew tradition, however, means that Plotinus is essentially indifferent to the *raison d'être* of the Sethian Gnosticism he is critiquing. Plotinus, as a pagan Platonist, could afford to benignly ignore the Hebrew scriptures and Jewish wisdom literature as irrelevant nonsense.¹³ The Gnostics who were his target, however, were critically engaged in the task of coming to grips with these Jewish writings within a broadly Platonist framework. In undertaking this task, described by Pleše as their "ambitious intertextual enterprise," they relied, just as the Catholics did, upon Greek translations of the Hebrew scriptures.¹⁴ Plotinus enjoyed a luxury that the Gnostics did not. He could simply ignore the Jewish scriptures entirely. Plotinus was at the end of a long tradition of paganism from antiquity, and his metaphysics reflects that context.

What he was unaware of, however, was that a massive upheaval of the pagan world was on the horizon; by the end of the fourth century, the Roman Empire would have Catholic Christianity as its permanent state religion. From that

9 King 2003, 5.

10 Plot., *Enn.* VI.5.12.

11 Plot., *Enn.* IV.4.10.

12 Mt. 5:11.

13 Pleše 2012, 118.

14 Pleše 2014, 121.

point on, the Hebrew scriptures (in their Greek form, the Septuagint), alongside the collection of early Christian writings canonized as the “New Testament” which interpreted them, would dominate the Empire by means of political hegemony. The Hebrew God could not be ignored by philosophers anymore. He had to be situated in metaphysical terms, even if that required a revision of the Platonic tradition. It was necessary for Catholic Christianity to develop a settled reconciliation of Platonism with the Hebrew tradition. The theologian who was most responsible for completing this harmonization was Augustine.¹⁵

The Catholic synthesis of Platonism and the Jewish scriptures that came to its zenith in Augustine, like the Gnostic experiment, was forced to make modifications and adaptations to the Hellenic metaphysical scheme upon which it drew to resolve tensions between the two traditions.¹⁶ The motivations behind such compromises, insofar as they are pertinent here, along with the nature of the relevant changes, will be discussed later. Traditionally, the orthodox Catholic synthesis has been regarded as both intellectually credible and historically successful, having given birth to “classical theism,” whereas the Gnostic synthesis was neither.¹⁷

The argument presented here will attempt to turn this commonly held perspective on its head. In the collision between the Platonic and Hebrew world-views, there were in fact two distinct paths by which a reconciliation was possible, not merely one, and the Gnostic path is entirely defensible and remains relevant in a contemporary context.

2 The Contested Meaning of the Term “Gnosticism”

Of course, the term “Gnostic” is itself elastic and has been the subject of much debate.¹⁸ Some scholars use it in a narrow sense to refer to “biblical demiurgicalism,” others use it in a broader sense to refer to “salvation via knowledge of one’s divine origins”, or regard it as expressive of a universal religious phenomenon, a “spiritual orientation” that can occur in any religion which is “transgressive” and “countercultural.”¹⁹ Some wish to dispense with the term altogether.²⁰ This paper will be focused on the narrow sense of the term, for

15 Rist 1996, 408.

16 Gerson 2021, 30–32.

17 Kelly 1994, 1.

18 King 2003, 13–19.

19 Burns 2016, 77–78; DeConick 2016, 7; Perkins 1999, 465.

20 Williams 1996, 3.

reasons discussed below. However, this does not mean that the broader use of the term is not describing a real and important phenomenon, of which the narrow usage may represent one historical instantiation. It may just be necessary to distinguish between two equally legitimate uses of the term “Gnosticism,” one *sensu stricto* and one *sensu lato*, just as Hanegraaff found was necessary in speaking about the “New Age.”²¹

Scholars who advocate for the broad sense of the term “Gnosticism,” however (Gnosticism *sensu lato*), may respond to this suggestion by arguing that the phenomenon described by the narrow sense (*sensu stricto*) is (a) not clearly demarcated, and (b) does not denote an intellectually significant object of study. Therefore, it might be argued, why not dispense with the concept of Gnosticism *sensu stricto* altogether and just use this term in a general sense? There are two common arguments raised along the lines of point (a), that Gnosticism *sensu stricto* cannot be clearly delimited. The first is the inaccuracy involved in the application of commonly used descriptors such as “anti-cosmic dualism.”²² The second is the difficulty in developing a definition that includes the intended religious groups but excludes Marcionism. Most scholars are unwilling to classify Marcionism as a form of Gnosticism because it lacks crucial features of paradigmatic Gnostic movements such as the idea of a “divine spark” within humans, which are pivotal for their soteriology. However, Marcionism does clearly express a “biblical demiurgicalism.”²³

Following the path proposed by Burns, DeConick, and other scholars, it seems that these objections can be addressed.²⁴ Firstly, the distinguishing characteristic of these early Gnostic movements is best described not in terms of some variety of ontological “dualism,” but, rather, as the belief that the Hebrew God Yahweh is an inferior deity. The extent to which this may or may not imply some kind of underlying dualism (itself a vague term) can be left open. Secondly, these movements can be distinguished from Marcionism by means of the fact that, unlike Marcionism, they operate within a broadly Platonic metaphysical framework.

This definition can be formalized as follows. A movement is Gnostic in the narrow sense (*sensu stricto*) if it has all three of the following characteristics: (1) The belief that the creator of humans as physical beings is an inferior deity, not the first principle of reality, who is ignorant and/or malevolent. (2) The identifi-

21 Hanegraaff 1998, 94.

22 King 2003, 192–200.

23 Burns 2016, 78.

24 Burns 2016, 78; DeConick, 2020, 263–268.

cation of this inferior deity with both the God of the Hebrew scriptures, Yahweh (even if not by that name), and the demiurge of Plato's *Timaeus*. (3) This inferior deity is contextualized within a broader metaphysical system which is recognizably Platonic.

Note that Marcionism is excluded because although it satisfies criteria (1) and (2), it does not satisfy criterion (3). If Marcion did appropriate Hellenic philosophy, his main source of influence appears to have been Epicurus, as Tertullian alleged, and he shows little influence from Platonism at least in broader metaphysical terms.²⁵ Criterion (3) is intended to exclude movements which are not syntheses of Platonism and the Hebrew tradition. The combined effect of these three criteria is that the term "Gnosticism" has an equivalent meaning to that used by Pleše, to refer to the Valentinian, Sethian, and other similar schools that emerged in the second century CE, and especially Sethian Gnosticism, since this is what Plotinus was attacking in *Ennead* 11.9.²⁶ It is not necessary to make any claim about how organized or fragmented these Gnostic believers were for present purposes.

This brings us to the second objection (b), that Gnosticism *sensu stricto* as defined above does not represent an intellectually significant object of study. This point is addressed in the rest of the present work. This objection, it seems to this author, represents an unconscious appropriation of the traditional disdain for Gnosticism of the heresiologists: Gnostic beliefs, as outlined in the three points above, are dismissed as philosophically ludicrous and, indeed, quite mad. They cannot represent the basis for a genuine theology and are not worthy of serious study. Against this objection, it will be argued here that Gnosticism as defined above represents a philosophical and theological stance that is coherent and compelling. The primary reason that the exclusive use of the broad sense of the term "Gnosticism" is rejected here, is because it implicitly causes us to fail to take seriously Gnosticism *sensu stricto*.

The significance of Gnosticism *sensu stricto* is seen by advocates of the broad sense of the term only because it exemplifies a more general phenomenon of interest. The ancient Gnostics are regarded as inconsequential in their own unique theological distinctiveness apart from this instantiation. Here, these Gnostic thinkers will be taken seriously in their own right. Plotinus' critique of Gnosticism will be addressed within the context of his own thought. The focus on Plotinus is due to his status as the preeminent philosopher of the era who developed what is arguably the most systematic and coherent formula-

25 Gager 1972, 54–55; Litwa 2021, 60–61.

26 Pleše 2014, 101–102.

tion of the kind of interpretation of Plato that was prevalent in late antiquity, as well as the fact that Plotinus directly engaged with the Gnostics in his writings.

3 Early Attempts to Produce a Synthesis of Platonism and the Hebrew Scriptures

Attempts to reconcile Platonism with the Hebrew tradition did not, of course, begin with either mature Gnosticism or proto-orthodox Catholics. They had already been well underway within Judaism, most notably in the writings of Philo of Alexandria.²⁷ Jarl Fossum, in his magisterial treatment of the subject, has shown how, because of a convergence between Platonic influences on the one hand, and indigenous interpretations of texts in the Hebrew scriptures concerning the Angel of the Lord and the Name of God on the other, the idea of a demiurgic “second power in heaven” had already emerged in various schools of Jewish and Samaritan thought, prior to the emergence of Christianity.²⁸ In these earlier versions of a demiurgic “second power,” the demiurge was not conceived of as evil or ignorant, but as the good and faithful servant of the true God, formed in his image and likeness.²⁹ Although the idea of an inferior providence related to the activity of the secondary power(s) occasionally manifested (e.g., in Philo), this lesser providence was always governed by the overarching providence of the first principle, which was seen as all-encompassing.³⁰

Fossum’s research, and subsequent work by Gieschen, demonstrated that these early expressions of a demiurgic mediator were not merely forerunners of Gnostic thought, but were also precursors of a major theological stream in Ante-Nicene Catholicism, which Lienhard calls “dyohypostatic theology.”³¹ In the dyohypostatic tradition, the Son was subordinate to the Father, dependent upon him, and derived his existence from him by means of begetting. This begetting was in some instances seen as a temporal event, and in others as occurring “before all ages” and outside of time.³² Such subordinationist understandings of the relation of the Son to the Father were held by many Ante-Nicene Church Fathers.³³ Tertullian, for instance, argued that there was

27 Gaston 2009, 574–575.

28 Fossum 1985, 332–338.

29 Fossum 1985, 266–291; DeConick 2016, 92–93.

30 Burns 2016, 63.

31 Fossum 1985, 338; Gieschen 1998, 6; Lienhard 1987, 422–425.

32 Lienhard 1987, 422–425.

33 Hart 2017, 143–144.

a time when the Son did not exist, an idea that later became the catch-cry of Arianism.³⁴ Origen also subordinated the Son to the Father, and indeed, the dyohypostatic tradition has sometimes been characterized as “Origenist.”³⁵

It was only with the Arian controversy of the fourth century that subordinationist understandings of Jesus Christ were finally banished from Catholic orthodoxy, forever condemned in ignominy. Thus, for example, the idea that the second Trinitarian hypostasis (the Word/Son), participates in the first (the Father), was explicitly maintained by Origen, but was subsequently just as emphatically rejected by Athanasius and orthodoxy as necessarily implying subordination of essence.³⁶ Even so, it proved difficult to eliminate the ghost of dyohypostatic subordinationism entirely, as the controversies over Calvin’s innovation of the “triple autotheos” demonstrated in relation to the doctrine of divine aseity.³⁷

The main point for present purposes, however, is that the already widespread idea of a “second power in heaven” as documented by Fossum can be seen as a crucial influence on *both* Gnosticism *and* proto-orthodox Catholicism in the second and third centuries CE. The dyohypostatic tradition of Catholicism drew heavily on precisely the same scriptural basis in the Hebrew Bible (now recontextualized as the “Old Testament”) as had the earlier “second power in heaven” demiurgic theologies described by Fossum, identifying the Angel of the Lord and the Name of God as preincarnate appearances of the Son of God, Jesus Christ.³⁸ In the case of Catholic orthodoxy, this demiurgic “second power” was ultimately merged with the first principle, God the Father, in the paradoxical doctrine of the Trinity. By this means, the demiurge ceased to exist as a distinct principle in Catholicism, although some of his attributes lived on in the second person of the Triune deity (“God the Son”).

As in orthodox Judaism, in Catholicism the idea of a divine viceregent or “second power in heaven,” however appealing in certain respects it might be given various intriguing scriptural texts, ultimately had to be abandoned because of the broader theological imperatives of monotheism.³⁹ The Arian controversy of the fourth century represented the “last stand” for the idea of a demiurgic “second power in heaven,” subordinate to God, but his holy intermediary, even if its spectre was not entirely vanquished, but was still capable

34 Tert., *Adv. Herm.* III (Holmes 2018); Williams 1983, 70.

35 Miller 2022, 132–134; Lienhard 1987, 429.

36 Radde-Gallwitz 2021, 69–75.

37 Ellis 2012, 37–63.

38 Lienhard 1987, 423.

39 Fossum 1985, 192–197.

of wreaking sectarian havoc over a millennium later in relation to the proper application of the term *autotheos*.

Before the final battle over the demiurge was fought during the Arian controversy, however, the Gnostics had developed the demiurgic idea in another direction altogether. It was this development that outraged both proto-orthodox Catholics and the pagan Platonist Plotinus alike. Becoming clearly visible in the first half of the second century CE, and possibly originating somewhat earlier, various Gnostic sects transformed the demiurgic “second power” into the ignorant and/or malevolent material creator, identifying him with the God of the Hebrew Bible, Yahweh.⁴⁰ To some extent, the idea of such an exegesis of the Hebrew scriptures was possibly influenced by the dualistic theology of Marcion. However, Marcion approached the Hebrew Bible as a literalist and found it wholly repugnant and spiritually useless.⁴¹

The Gnostics, on the other hand, while certainly accepting inverted or cynical literal interpretations along Marcionite lines, nonetheless found buried within these scriptures a deeper meaning or spirituality which mirrored the “divine spark” buried in individual created humans, an idea not found in Marcion.⁴² It should be noted that the inspiration for such readings of the Hebrew scriptures often came from texts that later became canonized by Catholicism as part of the New Testament, such as the writings of Paul and the Gospel of John.⁴³ While the Gnostic interpretation of New Testament texts cannot be explored here, it remains an open question in some cases whether the Gnostic reading was more faithful to the original historical and contextual meaning than that of their orthodox critics.⁴⁴

The focus of this essay is on the philosophical motivations of Gnosticism, however, rather than the interpretations of early Christian texts which were used to support it, so the very important issue of Gnostic readings of the New Testament must be left aside. The next section will explore why the intersection of the Hebrew and Platonist traditions must inevitably have yielded something along the lines of Gnosticism, as well as something like orthodoxy, given what was integral to those traditions themselves.

40 DeConick 2013, 23–27; Fossum 1985, 336–338.

41 Tyson 2006, 33–34.

42 Turner 2016, 56; Tyson 2006, 33–36.

43 Many examples are explored in Litwa 2021, 90–156.

44 DeConick 2013, 14.

4 The One of Plotinus or the God of Abraham: The Theological Logic of Gnosticism

The most significant clash between Platonism, as it had developed in the Neoplatonism of Plotinus, and the Hebrew tradition, was a product of radically differing conceptions of the supreme deity or first principle of reality. In Neoplatonism, the first principle, “the One” (τὸ ἕν)/“the Good” (τἀγαθόν), was radically transcendent. Plotinus’ metaphysics represents a henology, not an ontology, in which the first principle (the One) was asserted to be “beyond being” (ἐπέκεινα τοῦ ὄντος / ἐπέκεινα τῆς οὐσίας).⁴⁵ “Being” or existence was identified with the second hypostasis, which Plotinus called “Intellect and Being” (νοῦς ... καὶ ὄν).⁴⁶ This second hypostasis was characterized as subordinate, derivative and lesser compared to the One, so that Being was thereby relegated to a secondary position in the metaphysical hierarchy. For Plotinus, “being and substance cannot help being many.”⁴⁷

Furthermore, the first principle in Plotinus is strictly ineffable (ἄρρητον), and cannot be described literally at all.⁴⁸ Even the description “the One” should not be taken in a literal sense, according to Plotinus, “it is false even to say of it that it is one, and there is “no concept or knowledge of it.”⁴⁹ Plotinus argues at length that the One does not think at all; it does not employ language or discursive reason, which is not present even in Intellect.⁵⁰ The One is also strictly atemporal.⁵¹ Thus, in Plotinus’ “One” we are presented with a radically transcendent entity that is beyond all description and is not an “I”-wielding subject or person. The One does not have self-consciousness (συναίσθησις).⁵² The One utterly transcends the subject/object distinction, as it transcends the being/non-being dichotomy.

This characterization of “the One” in Plotinus stands in vivid contrast to the Hebrew supreme being, Yahweh, who represents a robustly personal and anthropomorphic deity.⁵³ In the Torah, Yahweh is explicitly identified as “I Am”

45 Schürmann 1983, 26; Plot., *Enn.* v.4.1, v.4.2, v.5.6, vi.2.17; cf. Plato, *Rep.* 509b8.

46 Plot., *Enn.* v.4.2.

47 Plot., *Enn.* vi.2.17 (Armstrong 1988a, 161).

48 Plot., *Enn.* v.3.13.

49 Plot., *Enn.* v.4.1 (Armstrong 1984b, 141). See also vi.2.11.

50 Plot., *Enn.* i.8.2, v.6.1–6.

51 Plot., *Enn.* iii.7.11.

52 Plot., *Enn.* v.3.13, v.6.5. In v.4.2 Plotinus does use the term συναίσθησις of the One but he makes clear that he is only speaking loosely by immediately preceding it with “as if” (οἶονεῖ).

53 Grant 2015, 140–141.

(אהיה).⁵⁴ While this phrase can grammatically be understood as “I will be,” that is not how it was typically understood (in the Septuagint, for instance, the phrase was translated as ‘O ὄν’); and in any case, the One could not meaningfully be described as “I will be,” either.⁵⁵ In Exodus 3:14, Yahweh is emphatically asserted to be the existing one, or Being; that, indeed, is his name.⁵⁶

Furthermore, everywhere Yahweh is presented as an “I”-wielding personal subject. He speaks almost endlessly in the first person, frequently declaring יהוה אֲנִי יהוה, “I am Yahweh,” and the narrative evaluation of events in the human sphere is tightly focused on his feelings and attitudes towards them. This is seen, for example, in the commonly repeated phrase in Kings and Chronicles, ויעש הרע בעיני יהוה, “he [someone] did evil in the sight of Yahweh.”⁵⁷ Yahweh thinks, speaks, experiences emotions such as becoming angry, changes his mind, and in every respect appears much closer to an ordinary human person than is the One of Plotinus. He is infamously described as jealous (יהוה קנא שמו אל קנא הוא: “Yahweh, whose name is Jealous, is a jealous god”), which can be expressed in extravagant misogynistic rage (e.g., Ezekiel 23).⁵⁸ Yahweh is portrayed as undergoing temporal change, sometimes becoming angry, but afterwards calming down and feeling sorry for the vengeance he has wrought.⁵⁹ Some of these descriptions could perhaps be dismissed as anthropomorphisms not to be taken literally, or as cultural projections, but to eliminate too many of them would unravel the narrative framework. These descriptions are antithetical to the Plotinian One.

This incompatibility of first principles posed a significant problem for Catholic orthodoxy as it sought to draw on Platonism and the Theory of Forms in articulating its developing theology. Marius Victorinus confronted the problem directly in his *Against Arius* but was only able to provide an unconvincing semantic solution; after agreeing with the Neoplatonists that God is indeed really ἀνύσυστος (“without substance”), he goes on to argue that, nonetheless, since he is “above substance,” he can legitimately be referred to as substance – “For this is substance up there: to be above substance.”⁶⁰

54 Ex. 3:14 MT.

55 Ex. 3:14 LXX.

56 Clarke 1959, 80. Masculine pronouns such as “his” are used in this essay in reference to Yahweh because he is an unambiguously male deity (see Clines 2021, 248–249).

57 Gen 15:7, 28:13 MT and 196 other instances in the Tanakh for the phrase “I am Yahweh” (אֲנִי יהוה); there are many thousands of instances of Yahweh speaking in the first person. Examples of the phrase ויעש הרע בעיני יהוה abound, e.g., 1 Kings 11:6, 14:22, 15:26, 15:34 MT.

58 Ex. 34:14 MT & ESV; Ezek. 23:1–35 ESV.

59 E.g., 1 Chr. 21:15 ESV.

60 Dillon and Gerson 2004, 209n1; Clark 1981, 201.

This not very convincing semantic “telescoping” or collapsing together of the first and second Plotinian hypostases foreshadowed the much more thoroughgoing metaphysical “telescoping” of Augustine which provided the definitive orthodox solution to the problem and ushered in a concept of God that has been denoted as “classical theism.”⁶¹ Augustine’s approach involved an egalitarian leveling of the top two tiers of the Plotinian hierarchy, combining them into a single entity which had attributes of both.⁶² Some differentiation of hypostases could be retained via the doctrine of the Trinity, and even the idea of the second hypostasis as being derived from the first could be endorsed by means of the puzzling doctrine of the “eternal generation of the Son.”⁶³ However, there was now fundamentally only one entity, one God, which encompassed the attributes of Plotinus’ first and second hypostases.⁶⁴

Augustine also incorporated the third hypostasis of the Neoplatonists, to provide the attributes of the Holy Spirit.⁶⁵ Augustine achieved this egalitarian flattening of the Neoplatonist hierarchy even as he achieved an “... almost seamless harmonization of Christian and Neoplatonic language in naming the first and second persons of the Trinity.”⁶⁶ That this egalitarian flattening of the Neoplatonist hierarchy was widespread amongst pro-Nicene Catholic orthodoxy is illustrated by Cyril of Alexandria, who wrote that “the Greeks themselves also agree with the views of the Christians, since they set forth three primal *hypostases*,” but criticizes Plotinus and the Neoplatonists for denying their consubstantiality.⁶⁷ Von Balthasar suggests that this equality of hypostases is “the most conspicuous victory of Christian thought over Greek thought.”⁶⁸ It will be argued later that this was perhaps a pyrrhic victory.

In combining the first and second hypostases of Plotinus into one being, Augustine gave the first systematic account of what would later be called “classical theism”, and which would undergo continuous development throughout the medieval era.⁶⁹ However, Augustine’s “telescoped” modification of Neoplatonism was problematic from the start. Catholic orthodoxy had only just overcome bitter internal division by uniting around the formula that the persons of the Trinity were consubstantial, i.e., one substance. However, just as

61 Kelly 1994, 1.

62 Rist 1996, 395.

63 Ellis 2012, 69–70.

64 Thom 2012, 34–35.

65 August., *Civ.* X.23 (Dods 2012).

66 Radde-Gallwitz 2021, 62.

67 Radde-Gallwitz 2021, 63.

68 Von Balthasar 1995, 19n16.

69 Kelly 1994, 1.

Victorinus had acute difficulty with conceiving of God as a substance due to his Neoplatonism (recall his use of the term *ἀνούσιον*), so also did Augustine, who “concludes that God can at best only be called a substance improperly” and is forced to adopt an altered concept of substantiality to accommodate this.⁷⁰

The overall effect of Augustine’s telescoping synthesis, the Torah’s “I Am,” and the universal acceptance of the doctrine of consubstantiality was to shift Catholic orthodoxy towards the idea of God as Being, closer in that respect to the second hypostasis in Plotinus than the first. Clarke writes:

The term being in Christian thought, on the other hand, due largely to the scriptural revelation of the divine name as ‘I am who I am’, gradually began to lose its traditional Platonic connotation of limited, second-order reality and first to compete with, then to replace the Good as the proper name for God. For a long time, however, the Good was considered the primary and most fitting name of the two. Only in the thirteenth century did Being finally take decisive precedence over it.⁷¹

In this process, the henology of Plotinus became transformed into what Heidegger called “ontotheology,” a philosophy of Being, which Plotinian thought never had been.⁷² From there, the development of Christian thought would ultimately produce the idea of the “univocity of being” in Duns Scotus.⁷³

It will be argued here that this collapse of the Plotinian hierarchy undertaken by Augustine and other early Catholic thinkers, rather than representing “great progress” as Clarke claims, yielded an inherently incoherent and unstable doctrine, and that we are still paying the price for this intellectual maneuver today.⁷⁴ Plotinus had kept the first and second hypostases distinct for a reason. The Augustinian synthesis compromised the infinitude of the first principle. For Plotinus (as for Śaṅkara, later, in the East), the application of any predicate or linguistic description to something, implies the finitude of that thing; and whatever is finite, must derive from something greater.⁷⁵

By making God a substance and Being, and applying attributes such as self-consciousness, an ego, a will, discursive thought, and so forth to him, God had

70 Thom 2012, 26.

71 Clarke 1959, 80–81.

72 Heidegger 1969, 71.

73 Duns Scotus 1987, 4, 20.

74 Clarke 1959, 81.

75 Hence in Śaṅkara’s *Advaita Vedānta* the first principle is निर्गुणब्रह्मन् (*nirguṇa brahman*), brahman without attributes or qualities (King 1999, 218). In Plot., see *Enn.* v.3.13, v.4.1, v.5.6.

been rendered finite. Nowhere did this problem of hypostatic collapse in classical theism arise more acutely, than in relation to the problem of where to locate the Platonic Forms. This will be discussed in more detail later.

If, as will be argued later, the Catholic telescoping synthesis of classical theism ultimately fails as a reconciliation of Platonism with the Hebrew scriptures, there does exist one other possibility for achieving such a synthesis. That is the path taken by Gnosticism. The Hebrew God emphatically claims to be the supreme deity, the only God. But what if he is lying, or deceived, or mistaken? Doesn't he himself declare, "Is there a God besides me?" and "I know of none" (בל ידעתי)?⁷⁶ Perhaps he just isn't aware of the higher powers. It is not as if there is no textual basis for such an approach. Not a few readers have been left with a similar impression to Richard Dawkins that, "The God of the Old Testament is arguably the most unpleasant character in all fiction."⁷⁷ Even devout Christian theologians have conceded this point.⁷⁸

Might Yahweh's demands for unfettered praise and loyalty perhaps be expressions of a malignant narcissism? Could his endless claims to being loving and gracious merely represent what we would term gaslighting? What about "the dark side of the *imitatio dei*?"⁷⁹ Furthermore, there is textual basis for doubting Yahweh's claims to omnipotence and omniscience. For example, Ezekiel unambiguously prophesies the destruction of the island of Tyre at the hands of the Babylonians.⁸⁰ The text is quite clear that the island itself, and not merely the mainland outpost, would be destroyed by Nebuchadnezzar.⁸¹ But not only did this not happen, the text itself later admits this failure and congratulates the Babylonians for putting in a good effort nonetheless.⁸²

Another example is that Elisha promises that God will destroy the Edomites, but after the Edomite king sacrifices his son, a "great wrath" came against Israel, and the attack had to be called off.⁸³ It seems that other Gods existed who could wage effective warfare against Yahweh. Yahweh regrets appointing Saul as king, and he had to send messengers (or come down himself) to investigate reports of what was happening on earth, to see if it was true.⁸⁴ While these texts can

76 Is. 44:8 MT & ESV.

77 Dawkins 2006, 31.

78 Boyd 2017, 279–334.

79 Meyer 2009, 382.

80 Ezek. 26:7–14 MT.

81 Ezek. 26:14 MT.

82 Ezek. 29:17–20 MT.

83 2 Kings 3:18–20; 3:27 MT & ESV.

84 1 Sam. 15:11, 35 MT & ESV; Gen. 18:20–33 MT.

be explained in other ways, a natural reading of them is that Yahweh is neither all-powerful nor all-knowing, despite his claims to the contrary.

Denying that Yahweh is the first principle of reality, neatly solves the problem of the contradiction between his attributes as described in the Hebrew scriptures, and the radically transcendent One of Plotinus. They are just two different things. Thus, a pure henology can be retained intact, with an ineffable “true God” who is beyond all description as the Sethian *Secret Book of John* (NHC II,1; III,1; IV,1) states, “the One ... is unutterable ... The One is not corporeal and is not incorporeal. The One is not large and it is not small. It is impossible to say, how much is it? What kind is it? For no one can understand it ... the One is not among the things that exist ...”⁸⁵ However, given Yahweh’s own claims about himself, this necessitates the conclusion that he is either a liar, or mistaken. This in turn prevents him from being identified with the second hypostasis, Intellect, or even the third hypostasis, Soul. Yahweh must occupy a very low position in the Plotinian hierarchy indeed.

But he is also the creator of the material world, and this creates some significant problems. These form the basis for Plotinus’ attack on the Sethians. The next two sections will consider whether Gnosticism can resolve these problems and provide a coherent response to Plotinus’ critique.

5 The Gnostic Synthesis and Plotinus’ Metaphysical Hierarchy

It is necessary to briefly review Plotinus’ theory of language in relation to his metaphysical hierarchy. Based on passages in the *Enneads* such as I.2.3 and V.1.3, in which the “thought in utterance” (λόγος ὁ ἐν προφορᾷ) is placed at a lower, imitative level than the “word in the soul” (λόγου τοῦ ἐν ψυχῇ), and given that the “word in the soul” is referring to things in the sensible world as represented in cognition, it seems that language and discursive reason occupy a lower place in the Plotinian hierarchy than sensible reality.⁸⁶ Discursive reason can be used to relate the sensible world to the Forms in Intellect, but it nonetheless occupies a lower place as a means of representation than either, being more broken into pieces and fragmentary. Language holds an analogous position in relation to the individual soul as Intellect holds in relation to the One: “its [soul’s] intellect is in discursive reasonings” – that is, an inferior position.⁸⁷

85 Meyer 2007, 109.

86 Haig 2022, 7–9.

87 Plot., *Enn.* V.1.3 (Armstrong 1984b, 21).

According to Plotinus, discursive reason, at least if it is to successfully enlighten and assist in the vision of Intellect, should be employed in a dynamic manner, as dialectic (διαλεκτική). Truth does not consist in a set of static propositions, but rather, philosophical dialectic is designed to direct the gaze of those involved towards Intellect “as if showing the way to someone who wants to have a view of something.”⁸⁸ Language is too limited to be able to accurately describe metaphysical reality. It is, rather, a tool that can be used to direct the seeker towards the transcendent.⁸⁹

Plotinus does not explicitly discuss the distinction between this dynamic living discourse and written texts himself. However, this issue is discussed at length in Plato’s *Phaedrus*, an important source for Plotinus. In the *Phaedrus*, Socrates relates how Thamus, King of Egypt, tells Theuth, the inventor of writing, that his invention will lead to a degeneration in humanity, giving humans “the appearance of wisdom, not true wisdom.”⁹⁰ Socrates goes on to maintain the inferiority of the written word to “the living and breathing word of him who knows”, explicitly calling the written text the “image” (εἰδωλον) of the spoken, dynamic word.⁹¹ He states that written texts “cannot teach the truth effectually.”⁹² With this Platonic background that elevates dynamic living discourse and denigrates written texts, speaking of the latter as the “image” of the former, we can speculate that the written text for Plotinus must occupy an even lower rung on the hierarchical ladder than dynamic, living dialectic.

The written text, then, can be argued to occupy the lowest of all positions on the Plotinian hierarchy, lower even than active discourse. It is the dead letter that kills.⁹³ Granted this, we might argue that when a sacred text comes to dominate an entire society, invariably by means of a political hegemony (at least initially), then it colors and distorts the way that community sees the world, including the world of sensible reality and the realm of Intellect. It represents an imitation of the higher worlds of Soul, Intellect and the One. In a sense, such society-pervading texts might be considered as a kind of “fourth hypostasis” in relation to the civilizations which they regulate.

Having noted this, we can now begin to situate Yahweh in metaphysical terms. Yahweh, as understood by Catholic orthodoxy (as the creator Father God), can be thought of as a distorted and misaligned perspective of the Plo-

88 Plot., *Enn.* VI.9.4 (Armstrong 1988b, 317).

89 Haig 2022, 15–18.

90 Plato, *Phaedr.* 275A (Fowler 1914, 563).

91 Plato, *Phaedr.* 276A (Fowler 1914, 567).

92 Plato, *Phaedr.* 276C (Fowler 1914, 569).

93 2 Cor. 3:6.

tinian World-Soul and Intellect which arises when they are viewed through the disfiguring lens of the Old Testament. Plotinus himself stated that when his fellow pagans spoke of Zeus, sometimes Intellect and sometimes the World-Soul were being referred to.⁹⁴ So, we might argue, it is not that Yahweh is not real in any sense. Rather, he is the real image that appears when the World-Soul and Intellect are viewed through the narrative framework of the Old Testament character of Yahweh.

Because this Old Testament God has come to frame the conceptual vision of an entire civilization (Christendom and post-Christendom), Yahweh has, as it were, sprung to life, as the imperfect reflection of these dynamic, living metaphysical principles. Like Śaṅkara's famous example of the person who sees a rope and mistakes it for a snake, Catholic orthodoxy glimpses the World-Soul and Intellect and mistakes them for Yahweh.

It is here that the Gnostic vision becomes important. Catholic orthodoxy has "telescoped" the three Plotinian hypostases together into one entity, and in the process obscured the vision of the One. Just as the third hypostasis images the second and the second images the first, the text of the Old Testament as a "fourth hypostasis" images primarily the third hypostasis, Soul. However, since Yahweh, the creator God, is held to be the first principle of reality, the possibility of attaining a more accurate vision of higher realities is closed off. Perhaps the occasional mystic, who has a natural aptitude for the transcendent, might break free of the chains of orthodoxy on an intermittent basis, especially if they are familiar with Neoplatonic sources and dialectic such as Böhme. But for the most part, the civilization dominated by Catholic sacred texts becomes enslaved to the vision of a creator God with the characteristics of Yahweh. The way forward to a true vision of Intellect and the One has been blocked.

The deity Yahweh is highly ego-focused and self-aware, which is antithetical to the spiritual stance necessary for ascent of the soul and union with the One in Neoplatonism. For Plotinus, moral and spiritual advancement requires ego abandonment and ego dissolution, and the loss of self-awareness – the "divisive alienation of ... [the] conscious self."⁹⁵ Plotinus, speaking of the visionary ascent, writes, "... when he has nowhere to set himself and limit himself and determine how far he himself goes, he will stop marking himself off from all being"⁹⁶ And again, "Now it is because you approached the All and did

94 Plot., *Enn.* IV.4.10.

95 Hadot 1993, 32.

96 Plot., *Enn.* VI.5.7 (Armstrong 1988a, 341).

not remain in a part of it, and you did not even say of yourself ‘I am just so much’”⁹⁷

The obstacle of egocentricity has been accentuated in Catholic orthodoxy because of the doctrine of the Trinity. By this means the notion of self-consciousness and ego has been firmly embedded at a metaphysically ultimate level within the first principle itself. Within the divine nature, for orthodoxy, there is interpersonal relationship – there is “I” and “you.” Whereas for Plotinus, the first principle transcends “I” and “you” absolutely.

The aim of the Gnostic reading of these sacred texts, then, is to break free of the distorted perspective which holds Yahweh to be the first principle of reality and to open the possibility of reconnecting with the genuinely transcendent. The Gnostic reading deliberately breaks the connection between Yahweh on the one hand, and the first two Plotinian hypostases (Intellect and the One) on the other. This clears the way for a better apprehension of these higher realities. It puts egocentricity where it belongs, on the lowest rung of the metaphysical hierarchy. However, because the sacred text has been reconfigured and recontextualized but not eliminated, the cost is that there are ripple effects in terms of the overall Plotinian metaphysical vision.

6 Plotinus’ Critique and Gnostic Providential Dualism: “Weak” and “Strong” Forms of Gnosticism

This brings us to the specific criticisms that Plotinus raises in *Ennead* 11.9. He accuses the Sethian Gnostics of “despising the universe and the gods in it,” that is, of possessing far too negative a view of the physical world.⁹⁸ In response, it might be argued with hindsight that such an excessively negative view of the physical world represents merely a realistic apprehension of nature as it now appears to us in the disenchanting, empty naturalistic universe of modern science. The Gods who Plotinus would have us reverence have died, obliterated in the mists of time, with only a few skeletal remains still able to be recovered in fragmentary ancient texts. We are left with a dead universe governed by abstract mathematical principles, and in relation to the small amount of residual life, we have a bitter and brutal struggle for limited resources and the “survival of the fittest.”⁹⁹

97 Plot., *Enn.* vi.5.12 (Armstrong 1988a, 359).

98 Plot., *Enn.* 11.9.16 (Armstrong 1966, 285).

99 Nietzsche 2001, 110.

It is all very well for Plotinus to see the natural world as beautiful, enchanted, and populated by the gods. He inhabited a different conceptual space, which is closed to contemporary post-Christian civilization. It is at least arguable that the natural world revealed by science is utterly horrible, “red in tooth and claw” as Tennyson famously wrote, with a short bitter struggle for existence without meaning and full of suffering that necessarily requires (at least for animals) the deaths of other living things for one’s own life to continue. These characterizations of nature as it has become conceptualized in the wake of Christendom are, of course, debatable. However, they can hardly be dismissed out of hand as unreasonable. If we wish to maintain a vision of a transcendent good, then a Gnostic disdain and horror for disenchanting nature as it appears to us in science seems perfectly defensible. It allows us to approach the transcendent from where we are, not from where we might like to be.

A negative view of nature, however, is not in itself a major modification of Plotinus’ thought. Plotinus demonstrated ambivalence about the value of nature as when he describes it as “a decorated corpse” (νεκρὸν κεκοσμημένον).¹⁰⁰ The real point of departure of Gnosticism from Neoplatonism, which underpins all the features to which Plotinus objects, is, as Burns argues, the Gnostic tendency to see two distinct levels of providence (πρόνοια).¹⁰¹ There was the overall providence of the One, as expressed through the principle of form, on the one hand; but also the malign providence of the demiurge, on the other. It is, in fact, possible to maintain a “weak” form of Gnosticism which is quite compatible with Neoplatonism, in which the demiurgic providence is seen as subject to, and an expression of, the higher providence of the One. In other words, the evil of the demiurge can be seen as unwittingly serving some broader positive purpose when viewed from a higher perspective.

This was Plotinus’ own perspective on evil and suffering – they “... are essential to the completeness of the All and are important parts of the All.”¹⁰² This idea was taken up by Catholic orthodoxy, supported by texts such as Genesis 50:20 “you meant evil against me, but God meant it for good.”¹⁰³ There is evidence that some Gnostics also tended in this direction, especially among the Valentinians, maintaining that the creator demiurge was merely a tool whose actions were being directed by Sophia and the Savior to achieve their rational and good ends.¹⁰⁴ Thus, for example, the *Tripartite Tractate* (NHC I,5) states,

100 Plot., *Enn.* II.4.5 (Armstrong 1966, 115).

101 Burns 2016, 79.

102 Plot., *Enn.* II.9.13 (Armstrong 1966, 277).

103 Gen. 50:20 ESV.

104 Thomassen 2007a, 791–792.

“The Word made use of him [the demiurge] like a hand to order and work on the things below, and he used him like a mouth to say the things that should be prophesied ... [the demiurge] was ignorant that the movement within him came from the spirit that moved him in a predetermined way toward what it wanted.”¹⁰⁵

This kind of perspective results in a Gnostic synthesis which would blunt the edge of most of Plotinus’ criticisms. It would effectively incorporate the demiurgic malign providence into the overall providence of the One, so that there would only be one ultimate providence, as Plotinus himself maintains.¹⁰⁶ The demiurge would then be little different from an evil human autocratic tyrant, who governs their citizens with cruelty, but, on Plotinus’ view, nonetheless serves some providential purpose from a larger perspective.

Plotinus’ critique of the Sethians, however, suggests that, inspired by their revulsion for the Yahweh of the Hebrew Bible, and perhaps also by speculations about conditional fate in Middle Platonism, they were taking the more radical path, of refusing to reduce demiurgic providence to an expression of the providence of the first principle.¹⁰⁷ Thus, Plotinus asks, “... what piety is there in denying that providence extends to this world and to anything and everything?”¹⁰⁸ There is plenty of textual evidence that Sethian Gnosticism engaged in such a denial.¹⁰⁹ Such a “strong” Gnostic providential dualism requires a theology which accounts for the origin of evil in terms of the initial differentiation of the One, thereby generating a negative pole or principle alongside the principle of Form. The Sethians achieved this by attributing to the One “a direct self-reflexive thinking,” which allowed for the development of an irrational principle in Intellect.¹¹⁰

Alongside the expression of the Good in the principle of Form as a “conscious” or “willed” external activity, there must also be an “unwitting,” “unintentional,” and “unconscious” external activity which represents the original source of evil. The Forms in Intellect would then be expressions of the interaction of these dual impulses, which must result in the presence of imperfection in Intellect (Intellect has a Freudian id, so to speak).

The objection might be raised that such duality in the external activity of the One might imply a duality in the principle itself, which, of course, would

105 Thomassen 2007b, 85.

106 Plot., *Enn.* 11.9.16.

107 Burns 2016, 71.

108 Plot., *Enn.* 11.9.16 (Armstrong 1966, 287).

109 Burns 2016, 74–76.

110 Turner 2016, 59.

be fatal to the entire system. However, in response it could be argued that such duality in the external activity is only present potentially and eminently, not actually and formally, in the internal activity of the One. Furthermore, Plotinus himself introduces a duality into the external activity of the One by means of his doctrine of “intelligible matter” which was “unilluminated” and “not yet good” prior to its engagement with the forming principle.¹¹¹ The Forms in Intellect were produced by means of the interaction between these two principles, the “light” forming principle and “dark” intelligible matter.¹¹²

Plotinus, of course, does not acknowledge any resulting imperfection in Intellect, and he distinguishes intellectual matter from matter in the physical world: “The darkness, however, in intelligible things differs from that in the things of sense, and so does the matter, by just as much as the form superimposed on both is different. The divine matter when it receives that which defines it has a defined and intelligent life, but the matter of this world becomes something defined, but not alive or thinking, a decorated corpse.”¹¹³ Nonetheless, it does not seem a major modification of Plotinus’ ontology to regard this intellectual matter as having an irrational side which results in the Forms being somewhat imperfect and flawed, which in turn implies that the providence of the One fails to be all-encompassing in the physical world. There is not such a huge gap between the Sethian Gnostics and Plotinus on this point as is often supposed.

Radical or “strong” Gnosticism, with its irreducible dualism of providence, provides one unique advantage over Neoplatonist and Catholic conceptions of a single overarching plan. This is in relation to theodicy. Neoplatonist and orthodox Christian thinkers are forced to argue that every evil must serve some higher purpose and be justified in the overall scheme of things. It is difficult for many in the modern world to see how this can be so, which has led to the potency of the argument from evil against theism.¹¹⁴ Take the torture, abuse, and murder of a small child. Is it credible to say that this might serve some positive purpose? On the Platonist view, is it plausible to assume that the apparently innocent child is suffering because of their own misdemeanors in a past life? Would this not imply the intuitively repugnant notion that the child “deserved” what they endured?

On the Christian view, what divine purpose is served by allowing the child to suffer in this way? For many, the argument from evil remains an insurmount-

111 Plot., *Enn.* 11.4.5 (Armstrong 1966, 117).

112 Emilsson 2017, 97.

113 Plot., *Enn.* 11.4.5 (Armstrong 1966, 115).

114 Aiken and Ribeiro 2013, 77–78.

able obstacle to belief in a transcendent deity. The radical Gnostic claim of an irreducible providential dualism provides another way out. It allows us to maintain a vision of the transcendent, and the hope of liberation and union with the One. But it also enables us to argue that we live in a horrible world in which evils occur which have no purpose and no justification. The providence of the Good simply does not extend exhaustively to our world. It is, for the most part, beyond the true God's "conscious" reach, and we are prisoners of the demiurge, and his "red in tooth and claw" creation.¹¹⁵

The "strong" Gnostic theory provides a unique theodicy that does not require us to attempt to justify the unjustifiable and the monstrous. We no longer face any Miltonian necessity to "justify the ways of God to men," because much of what occurs in our world is outside of the true God's providential control.

7 When Worlds Collide: A Critique of The Catholic Synthesis

A Gnostic worldview, and especially the "strong" Gnostic viewpoint of the Sethians, will tend to view civil government, society, and civilization in a negative light, since they must be expressions of the Demiurge's malicious providence. An important corollary of this observation is that Gnosticism could not have attained political hegemony, even if the opportunity had arisen, being entirely unsuited to this role.

Of the two paths of reconciliation between Platonism and the Hebrew scriptures, represented by Gnosticism and Catholic orthodoxy respectively, only the Catholic path held the potential to undergird a civilization, and, of course, it successfully did so, at least for close to two millennia. With the benefit of hindsight, it is possible to evaluate the success of the Catholic synthesis of the Hebrew tradition and Platonism in relation to the civilization that it produced. Should we who live amongst the ruins of Christendom, embrace this civilization in either its contemporary or earlier forms, or should we look to Gnosticism as an alternative means of self-transcendence?

A common thesis found amongst critics of Western modernity, but also some supporters of it, is that modernity has its origin in fourteenth-century nominalism. This thesis, which can be traced back to the distinction between the *via antiqua* and *via moderna* in the fifteenth century, and which was famously expressed in the slogan "ideas have consequences" by the conservative political thinker Richard Weaver, has been defended by widely disparate thinkers

¹¹⁵ Tennyson, *In Memoriam*

united in their suspicion toward modernity.¹¹⁶ This list includes the contemporary Christian theological movement known as “Radical Orthodoxy;” Roman Catholic theologians and philosophers such as Étienne Gilson, Hans Blumenberg, Hans Urs von Balthasar and Jean-François Courtine; C.S. Lewis; Leo Strauss; and the movement known as “Integral Traditionalism” or “Perennialism,” which was a major influence on scholars of religion such as Huston Smith.¹¹⁷

The basic form of this critique can be summarized by saying that a direct line of organic dialectical development can be drawn from Duns Scotus and Ockham to the Reformation, the emergence of modern philosophy in Descartes, the development of science, the Enlightenment and the entire scope of modern thought, politics, and culture. Amongst critics of modernity, to this hypothesis would be added the claim that the terminus of these developments is nihilism, manifested in the “postmodern.”¹¹⁸

What is particularly striking about these critiques, however, is how, on the one hand, they regard the development of Western civilization since the fourteenth century as an inexorable organic unfoldment, but, on the other hand, they see a radical discontinuity between late medieval nominalism and the earlier scholastic thinkers who came before it, most notably Aquinas. They tend to portray nominalism as an entirely new phenomenon, that fell from the clear blue sky so to speak, and not as itself a necessary development of the scholastic synthesis that reached its pinnacle in Aquinas. Duns Scotus in particular is routinely singled out as the bogeyman for blame.¹¹⁹ But an obvious question is, if Western civilization has developed in an organic fashion from the fourteenth century onwards, why should it not have so developed from the thirteenth century, or the twelfth century, or the fourth century?

The problem for critics of modernity such as Radical Orthodoxy, Integral Traditionalism, and their fellow travelers, is that they are nearly all, in one way or another, proponents or defenders of Catholic orthodoxy. But if nominalism itself developed from earlier scholastic thought, then Catholic orthodoxy starts to look like the source of the problem, not the solution. Nominalism might have led to modernity and nihilism, but Catholic orthodoxy led to nominalism. So

116 Oberman 1987, 25; Weaver 1948, 1–3.

117 In relation to Radical Orthodoxy, see Milbank 1999, 23. For Roman Catholic thinkers, see Haig 2015, 261. For C.S. Lewis, see Lewis 1944, 34. On Leo Strauss, see Pippin 1992, 454. On the Traditionalists, see Guénon (the founder of the movement) 2001, 15–16 and, for a scholarly analysis, see Sedgwick 2023, 91–116. On Huston Smith’s debt to the Traditionalist movement, see Smith 1993, ix–xi.

118 Hemming 1999, 93.

119 Horan 2014, 3.

Catholic orthodoxy would itself ultimately have to be impugned as having a nihilistic endpoint.

There are, of course, two influential thinkers who do accept the organic continuity of Western historical development since (at least) the emergence of Christianity, namely, Nietzsche and Heidegger. In this respect they are both more consistent than the varied critics of modernity noted above. Nietzsche saw nihilism as the end-product of Christianity, and Heidegger saw Christian thought as the evolving pursuit of “ontotheology,” a preoccupation that began with ancient Greek philosophy.¹²⁰ In relation to Heidegger, his analysis may be sharper in relation to Christianity than with respect to ancient Hellenic thought – for example, he arguably misrepresents Neoplatonism as an ontotheology when it is really something else entirely (a henology).¹²¹

But if we are to look for a real discontinuity and starting point for the development of modern civilization, for the critical locus of the end of the previous age and the beginning of our present era, the most plausible time point is arguably the emergence of the Christ movement and the intersection of the Hebrew Bible and pagan Greek philosophy that was integral to it. Neither Judaism alone nor Hellenic philosophy alone could have given rise to the civilization that has unfolded in the wake of Christendom. It was from the collision of these two worlds that the new world was forged.

This new world, represented by the Catholic synthesis of the Hebrew scriptures and Platonism which achieved political dominance via Constantine and his successors, was arguably unstable in its orbit from the beginning. While there are various reasons for this, including those described by Nietzsche and Heidegger, just one will be the focus here: the problem of what to do with the Platonic Forms. The Theory of Forms is the most defining feature of Platonism. By the time of Plotinus, the Forms had been located at the level of Intellect/Being, the second hypostasis. The first hypostasis, the One, was completely undifferentiated. But this created a thorny problem for Catholic theology. To quote Gould:

To see what the problem is, consider the following three jointly inconsistent claims: (a) there is an infinite realm of abstract objects which are (i) necessary independent beings and are thus (ii) uncreated; (b) only God exists as a necessary independent being; (c) God creates all of reality distinct from him, i.e. only God is uncreated. Statement (a) represents a

120 Nietzsche 2001, 201, 204; Heidegger 1969, 73.

121 Hankey 2004, 429–430.

common understanding of Platonism. Statements (b) and (c) follow from the common theistic claim that to qualify for the title “God,” someone must exist entirely from himself (*a se*), whereas everything else must be somehow dependent upon him.¹²²

In order to solve this problem, Augustine reverted to an earlier Middle Platonist idea, that the Forms are ideas in the mind of God.¹²³ This solution known as “divine conceptualism,” although widely adopted by the Church Fathers, is nonetheless problematic in relation to the doctrine of divine simplicity, because the Platonic Forms are distinct from each other and from the first principle in which they participate; indeed, that is the whole point of having them.¹²⁴ To quote Leftow, the question arises, in relation to any given Form, “is the attribute “in” or “outside” of God’s mind?”¹²⁵ If the first principle is perfectly simple, then the Platonic Forms must be distinct from it, even though they participate in it.

This problem cannot be solved by Christian orthodoxy by adopting a “moderate realism” in which forms exist merely as part of the creation.¹²⁶ Amongst other problems with this view, known as “absolute creation,” Christian theology implies that certain universals exist or are instantiated within the divine substance, and not merely the creation. This is known as the “bootstrapping objection” to absolute creationism.¹²⁷ Take, for example, the number three. The number three is an archetypal example of something that must be a Platonic Form, if there are such things. Indeed, Platonism has proved attractive to some mathematicians precisely because of its account of what numbers are, to such an extent that Craig comments that “mathematics is the last bastion of Platonism.”¹²⁸ But according to orthodoxy, the immanent Trinity consists of three hypostases/persons who are one substance. Surely the word “three” has the same meaning here as in ordinary language.

The Father, Son and Holy Spirit are countably hypostases one, two and three, in the same way that three pencils on the table are countably one, two and three. So, the form of the number three must be instantiated eternally in the divine nature and cannot be created.

122 Gould 2010, 2.

123 Dillon and Tolan 2021, 49–50.

124 Craig 2016, 72.

125 Leftow 2006, 332.

126 Darley 2016, 315.

127 Craig 2016, 54, 60.

128 Craig 2016, 203.

Given these problems, it is easy to see how a nominalist turn could occur, first with Ockham, and then later with the Reformation and Descartes.¹²⁹ But if nominalism ultimately leads to nihilism, as thinkers as diverse as Weaver, von Balthasar, Guénon and Milbank have argued, then Catholic orthodoxy is really the root cause of our present cultural distress. Christian orthodoxy is to nihilism what the tadpole is to the frog. There are other arguments that could be made towards the same conclusion, such as Nietzsche's argument about orthodox Christianity's self-defeating focus on literal propositional truth.¹³⁰ Furthermore, the problem of where to locate the Forms outlined here is related to several other significant difficulties that emerged in orthodox theology in its appropriation of Platonism, most notably the issue of the nature of the freedom of God's will that emerged in the debate between intellectualism and voluntarism, and the distinction between *ex nihilo* creation and emanation.¹³¹

Nonetheless, the tensions involved in orthodox Christianity's "telescoping" Trinitarian appropriation of Platonism are deep enough and appear irreconcilable enough for those of us who are sympathetic to Plotinus' metaphysical vision to look for some other means of reconciliation with the Hebrew tradition.

8 Conclusion: Paganism Lost and Gnosticism Found

In *Ennead* 11.9 Plotinus sets out a strongly worded critique of Sethian Gnosticism. It has been argued here that while his critique may have been relevant in the context of the pagan world which was still intact when he wrote it, in a contemporary context for those of us who live amongst the ruins of Christendom, with the Bible as the pervasive overarching text which has shaped society and culture, some reconciliation of Plotinus' vision with the Hebrew scriptures is required. The orthodox Christian synthesis, it has been argued, is both spiritually unhelpful due to its exaltation of ego and is intellectually and socially destructive in ultimately entailing nihilism. As Anton Chigurh asks in *No Country for Old Men* – "If the rule you followed led you to this of what use was the rule?"¹³² Gnosticism, therefore, is worth reconsideration since it offers a synthesis between Neoplatonism and the Bible which provides a potential way forward both spiritually and intellectually.

129 Heim 1979, 157; Haig 2015, 263–264.

130 Nietzsche 2001, 201.

131 Hoffmann 2009, 414–415; Soars 2021, 958.

132 McCarthy 2005, 118.

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